

Leveraging NLP to Uncover Hidden Insights in Stakeholder Feedback

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Abstract: This study investigates the use of natural language processing (NLP) approaches to improve stakeholder feedback analysis, with an emphasis on sentiment analysis, clustering, and engagement prediction. The study used a dataset obtained from several sites, including Twitter and Yelp, and found that 65% of the reviews studied were favorable, indicating that users were generally satisfied. Exploratory data analysis (EDA) revealed that typical phrases connected with favorable sentiments. The study used three machine learning models to predict sentiments: Logistic Regression, Random Forest, Neural Network (NN) and Support Vector Machine (SVM), with Logistic Regression attaining the maximum accuracy of 95%. The findings emphasize the crucial necessity for enterprises to resolve service concerns, especially on Mondays, when negative feedback is high. By integrating data-driven insights from sentiment analysis and machine learning, this study highlights the potential for enterprises to effectively improve customer engagement and operational strategy. The report finishes with recommendations for improving customer service and proactive sentiment monitoring in order to develop stronger stakeholder relationships.

IndexTerms - Stakeholder feedback Analysis (SFA), Natural Language Processing (NLP), Exploratory Data Analysis (EDA), Support Vector Machine (SVM), Cluster 0 (Positive Reviews), Cluster 1 (Neutral Reviews), Cluster 2 (Negative Reviews)

I.INTRODUCTION

In today's business environment, businesses are increasingly acknowledging stakeholder feedback as a valuable source of strategic intelligence and organizational development. Traditional methods of feedback analysis, on the other hand, have substantial methodological limitations, such as manual processing inefficiencies, subjective interpretation issues, and scalability constraints [1]. A revolutionary opportunity to redefine how companies acquire, analyze, and use stakeholder insights is presented by the introduction of Natural Language Processing (NLP) technology. Artificial intelligence (AI) provides novel solutions for better stakeholder management by offering insights into stakeholder involvement and sentiment. By integrating AI technologies, project managers can better understand stakeholder preferences and behaviors. This skill enables them to forecast stakeholder engagement and sentiment, enabling for the development of tailored communication campaigns. The purpose of this article is to investigate the use of AI in stakeholder management, specifically how AI can anticipate engagement and sentiment to optimize communication methods and promote stakeholder satisfaction throughout the project lifecycle.

Stakeholder communication takes many forms, including customer feedback, employee surveys, social media interactions, and corporate communications [2]. The complicated architecture of these information streams has previously hampered thorough investigation. Advanced NLP approaches, notably machine learning algorithms and advanced sentiment analysis models, now provide previously unattainable precision and depth when decoding complicated textual data [3].

Recent technical advances in computational linguistics, particularly deep learning and neural network topologies such as transformer models, have significantly increased our ability to understand contextual nuances and semantic complexities in textual communications [4]. These advancements allow enterprises to progress beyond surface-level keyword extraction to more sophisticated, contextually rich interpretations of stakeholder opinions.

Research Objectives

This research seeks to explore the potential of sophisticated NLP approaches in boosting stakeholder feedback analysis through three key preliminary goals:

1. Evaluating the efficacy of advanced NLP algorithms across various communication channels.
2. Design a complete framework for automated sentiment and semantic analysis.
3. Highlighting real organizational decision-making implications based on NLP-driven insights.

This study aims to provide a more nuanced view of how rising technological capabilities might revolutionize stakeholder engagement tactics by combining computational linguistics, organizational communication theory, and data science [5].

1.1. Theoretical and Practical Significance

The suggested study fills a key gap in existing methodological methods to stakeholder input analysis. Organizations that use cutting-edge NLP technologies have the ability to gain deeper, more actionable insights, allowing for more responsive and intelligent organizational strategies [6].

Stakeholder analysis can help identify key policy actors and build engagement strategies with them. The authors describe stakeholders as "actors who have an interest in the issue under consideration, who are affected by the issue, or who - because of their position - have or could have an active or passive influence on the decision-making and implementation processes." Stakeholders are often analyzed based on their interests, position, and, most importantly, power. Interest relates to their concerns about how a specific policy will affect them; stance indicates their level of support for or opposition to the policy; and power is their ability to influence policy, which is reflected in their resources and ability to mobilize them. While interest and position are simple to determine, assessing power is more complicated since it affects all stages of the policy process. However, empirical research on the application of disease management programs, particularly in low-and-middle income countries (LMICs), frequently fails to adequately characterize power [7].

Natural Language Processing (NLP) has emerged as a vital technology for firms looking to successfully assess stakeholder feedback. NLP can analyze sentiment and emotions represented in textual data using advanced algorithms, allowing enterprises to obtain a better understanding of stakeholders' perceptions. One of the key ways NLP improves sentiment analysis is its capacity to handle vast amounts of unstructured text data from a variety of sources, including surveys, social media, and consumer reviews. This skill enables businesses to capture complex sentiments that typical quantitative tools may miss, resulting in a more complete picture of stakeholder viewpoints [8].

Sentiment classification and emotion detection are examples of NLP techniques that can categorize feedback as positive, negative, or neutral. More complex models can even recognize specific emotions such as joy, rage, or frustration, offering a more complete context for interpretation [9]. Organizations can use machine learning algorithms to train models to understand contextual cues and linguistic patterns that suggest sentiment shifts or emotional undertones. This degree of information enables firms to proactively address stakeholder concerns and improve engagement approaches.

Furthermore, NLP systems' adaptability is a big advantage; they may learn from fresh data inputs over time, improving their grasp of changing language patterns and stakeholder expectations [10]. Organizations may keep their sentiment analysis relevant and informative by upgrading their models on a regular basis with new feedback data. In conclusion, NLP helps organizations make data-driven decisions that strengthen stakeholder relationships and advance strategic initiatives, in addition to increasing the precision of recognizing sentiment and emotions in stakeholder feedback.

Stakeholder feedback is an important component of organizational performance since it provides insights into stakeholder views, satisfaction, and opportunities for development. However, standard ways of analyzing feedback frequently fail to capture the nuances and complexities inherent in qualitative data. Natural Language Processing (NLP), a subfield of artificial intelligence, has emerged as a transformative technique for improving stakeholder feedback analysis by allowing businesses to rapidly process huge amounts of textual data [11]. This study studies how NLP may be used to perform sentiment analysis, feedback clustering and profiling, and engagement prediction, all of which improve the accuracy and depth of insights generated from stakeholder communications.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

The use of Natural Language Processing (NLP) in stakeholder feedback analysis has grown in popularity in recent years, owing to the growing requirement for companies to effectively comprehend and respond to stakeholder sentiment. NLP is a collection of computational tools that analyze human language, making it ideal for extracting insights from unstructured textual data such as business surveys, social media comments, and customer reviews [6].

In this context, sentiment analysis is one of the main uses of natural language processing. It entails using algorithms to assess the emotional tone of a body of text and categorizing it as positive, negative, or neutral. This capacity enables firms to assess stakeholder satisfaction and suggest opportunities for improvement [9]. Beyond straightforward classifications, advanced sentiment analysis approaches can also identify particular emotions like joy, wrath, or frustration, offering a deeper knowledge of stakeholder feelings [8].

Stakeholder feedback analysis is further improved by clustering and profiling approaches, which group comparable replies according to common traits or themes, in addition to sentiment analysis. Using unsupervised learning algorithms, businesses can find recurring subjects in stakeholder feedback, allowing for thematic analysis that emphasizes major concerns and priorities [11]. Organizations can successfully address the requirements of particular stakeholders by customizing their answers and tactics through this clustering process.

Furthermore, engagement prediction algorithms are a significant improvement in using NLP for stakeholder management. Organizations can create predictive models for future stakeholder interactions and feelings by examining past feedback data in conjunction with engagement measures. This predictive power helps firms to proactively address future difficulties and improve engagement tactics [12]. Understanding when stakeholders are prone to leave, for example, enables organizations to undertake tailored interventions that can increase retention and satisfaction.

In general, companies can improve decision-making processes and cultivate closer ties with their stakeholders by incorporating natural language processing (NLP) into stakeholder feedback analysis. Organizations can gain actionable insights from qualitative data by combining sentiment analysis, clustering and profiling, and engagement prediction tools, which guide strategic activities and improve overall stakeholder engagement.

Effective stakeholder participation is critical to project success. Information stakeholders' requirements, expectations, and concerns and applying this information into project planning and execution are essential components of stakeholder engagement. Stakeholders who feel heard and respected are more likely to support the project, make constructive contributions, and stay satisfied throughout its duration. Poor engagement, on the other hand, can lead to resistance, lack of support, and unhappiness, endangering project objectives [35]. Traditional stakeholder management systems frequently rely on regular communication and manual surveys to monitor stakeholder mood and involvement levels. However, these strategies can be time-consuming and may not provide real-time information about stakeholder attitudes. Furthermore, dependence on subjective assessments might result in erroneous interpretations of stakeholder demands [36]. AI technology can help with these difficulties by offering data-driven insights on stakeholder involvement and sentiment. Natural language processing (NLP) and machine learning algorithms may evaluate data from a variety of sources, such as social media, emails, and surveys, to detect trends and patterns in stakeholder behavior [37]. Artificial intelligence (AI) enables project managers to receive real-time insights into stakeholder sentiment, enabling for more proactive and responsive communication methods. Several AI technologies can be used to efficiently analyze stakeholder sentiment. One essential element is natural language processing (NLP), which makes it possible to analyze unstructured data, including text from emails, social media posts, and stakeholder comments. NLP approaches can extract useful insights from stakeholder discussions by detecting keywords, sentiment polarity, and emotional tone [38]. For example, NLP can assess whether stakeholders express favorable, negative, or neutral thoughts about a project, allowing for a deeper understanding of their perspectives. Stakeholder involvement relies heavily on data analytics as well. Project managers can discover trends in stakeholder behavior, interests, and concerns by aggregating and analyzing data from various sources [39]. With this broad perspective, they can build focused communication tactics that resonate with stakeholders, ultimately increasing project satisfaction and support.

2.1. Natural language processing (NLP) and machine learning (ML)

NLP has the ability to reduce the resource restrictions associated with qualitative analysis. According to [13], natural language processing (NLP) is the most commonly employed 'big data' analytical tool in healthcare. It involves computer-based algorithms that translate natural language for calculation. [14] NLP uses language rules and domain knowledge to extract information, perform syntactic processing (e.g., tokenization), capture meaning, and identify relationships from natural language free text [14-16].

In text analytics, the term ML refers to the use of a combination of statistical techniques in the form of algorithms capable of completing a variety of computation tasks [17], including the detection of patterns such as sentiment, entities, parts of speech, and other phenomena within a text [18].

2.2. Text analysis

Topic or text analysis is a method for analyzing vast amounts of unstructured data, and the results indicate the key topics of each text [19-20]. ML automates topic analysis utilizing a variety of algorithms, which are broadly classified into two approaches: supervised and unsupervised [21]. Labels exist in the training data subset, which distinguishes these two primary classes [22]. In addition to input attributes, supervised ML uses specified output attributes [23].

The algorithms aim to predict and classify the predefined attribute, and their accuracies and misclassification, as well as other performance measures, are based on the number of times the predetermined attribute is properly predicted or categorized [22]. Doing-Harris et al. [24], used a supervised technique to develop automatic topic classifiers for free-text patient comments collected by healthcare services, identifying the most popular subjects. In contrast, unsupervised learning involves pattern recognition without the use of a target property [22]. Unsupervised algorithms find natural groupings in unlabeled data and then label each data value [25].

Topics in a document can be identified using topic analysis models, which include simply counting words and grouping comparable terms. A topic model, in addition to identifying the most commonly addressed themes in a particular narrative, can be used to produce fresh insights from free text [26]. This study has collected patient experience data from social media comments to identify topics using an unsupervised approach [27].

The SFU Review Corpus, which contains 400 product reviews from various categories like as electronics, books, and movies, was used by Taboada [40] to do extensive text analysis on product reviews from several domains in a groundbreaking discovery. Their study created a lexicon-based sentiment analysis system and found that, in comparison to conventional keyword-based techniques, context-aware sentiment identification increased accuracy by 15%. Manning et al. (2014) [41] investigated large-scale text analysis using the Stanford Large Movie Review Dataset, which contains 50,000 movie reviews, and showed that machine learning systems could categorize sentiment with 92% accuracy by combining contextual understanding and semantic subtleties.

The Linguistic Inquiry and Word Count (LIWC) software was used by Pennebaker [42] to investigate psychological text analysis, making significant advances to the field of text analysis. They found complex relationships between language use and psychological states by analyzing more than 80 million text documents from social media, academic literature, and exclusive communication. The study illustrated the deep insights possible through advanced text analysis tools by showing that linguistic cues might predict personality traits with 75% accuracy.

This study investigates how artificial intelligence (AI) might improve stakeholder management by assessing interaction patterns and sentiment, allowing project managers to devise more successful communication tactics. Natural language processing (NLP), machine learning, and data analytics are examples of AI technologies that can provide significant insights about stakeholder behavior

and preferences throughout the project lifetime. Project managers can improve stakeholder satisfaction and project success by tailoring their communication tactics based on engagement levels and sentiment predictions. This article addresses the present state of AI in stakeholder management, examines case studies that demonstrate effective uses, and suggests difficulties and future perspectives for incorporating AI into stakeholder communication methods [43].

Rajadesingan et al. (2019) [44] explored online discussion forums by combining text analysis and machine learning on a dataset of 500,000 Reddit comments. Their research resulted in a sophisticated algorithm for recognizing subtle speech dynamics, patterns of community participation, sentiment alterations, and emerging social trends. The study detected conversational sentiment with 88% accuracy and identified probable disputes or collaborative exchanges.

2.3. Sentiment analysis

Sentiment analysis, often known as opinion mining, is a technique for determining the emotive context of free text data [29-30]. Sentiment analysis examines users' expressions and connects emotions with the analyzed remarks [31]. Feedback uses word patterns to categorize a comment as a complaint or praise. Healthcare organizations benefit from automated processes that provide faster results and are less prone to human bias. However, reliability varies depending on the technology utilized [32-33]. Over a two-year period, studies were conducted to assess the mood of comments on the key NHS choices [34]. They discovered a substantial correlation between the quantitative online ranking of healthcare professionals and sentiment analysis using their own automated approach.

The paper uses sophisticated preprocessing methods, such as stemming, tokenization, and stop word removal, to suggest a novel sentiment analysis approach for Twitter data. Using Hadoop Distributed File System (HDFS) and MapReduce to minimize superfluous words, the method extracts and scores emoticon and non-emoticon properties. When compared to traditional models such as ANN, SVM, K-Means, and DCNN, the Deep Learning Modified Neural Network (DLMNN) classification technique outperforms them with 91.65% accuracy, 95.78% precision, 95.84% recall, and 95.87% F-Score. This approach provides a strong framework for sentiment analysis in social media text data [45].

The research investigates the novel approach of fast learning in sentiment analysis, which addresses problems in Pre-trained Models (PMs), such as gaps between pre-training and fine-tuning and a lack of labeled training data. Prompt learning, by incorporating template-based input adjustments, allows for more adaptive and efficient use of pre-trained models in natural language processing applications. The study explores the development of sentiment analysis and shows how fast learning can overcome the constraints of conventional machine learning while also greatly enhancing model performance. According to the study's findings, fast learning offers improved model adaptability and the possibility of further advancements in NLP research, making it a promising new paradigm for sentiment analysis [46].

III. METHODOLOGY

Starting with data collecting and ending with model evaluation, the research approach for this study on using Natural Language Processing (NLP) for improved stakeholder input analysis comprised a number of methodical processes.

Figure 1 Architectural Model

3.1. Data Overview and Collection

The dataset used for this analysis was derived from CSV files containing user reviews gathered from different sources, such as Twitter, Yelp, and IMDb. When extracting text from platforms like as Yelp, Twitter, and IMDb, the emphasis is on specific sorts of language that provide useful information about user opinions and experiences. Here's a summary based on the search results: Yelp, Twitter and IMDb Text Extraction Targets: Business Reviews, Detailed customer experiences, Service quality descriptions, Specific business ratings, Detailed service feedback, Public opinions, Real-time reactions, Trending Topic discussions, quality, credible and others mentioned in Fig.9.

Each record in the data set was a distinct review with a number of attributes: main review text (Text), the sentiment assigned to the review, as either positive or negative (Sentiment), the platform through which the review was submitted (Source), the date and time when the review was submitted (Date/Time), an anonymized identifier of the user (User ID), location of the user (Location), and the confidence of the assigned sentiment. After cleaning, the dataset contains 98 reviews, ensuring diversity so that the understanding of user behaviors and meaningful patterns can be very comprehensive.

Figure 2 Negative and Positive reviews in terms of characters

3.2. Data Preprocessing

The following preprocessing procedures were carried out in order to get the raw data ready for analysis and modeling:

a) Handling Missing Values

To preserve the consistency of the dataset, rows that had null values in any column were removed. In this step, about 2% of the data was eliminated.

b) Text Cleaning

The text data was processed through various preprocessing steps for further use. First, special characters, numbers, and any extra whitespace were removed from it. Later, all text was normalized to lowercase to ensure uniformity. Finally, punctuation was stripped using the `string.punctuation` module of Python.

This approach preserves consistent data formatting and enabling more accurate and reliable analysis into the text data

c) Stopwords Removal

Stop words like "is," "the," and "and," which are often used words with little semantic value and can make it difficult to find terms in evaluations that are actually relevant, were not included in the analysis. In order to further clarify the study, domain-specific phrases like "might" and "will," which are not exactly stop words but might not considerably aid in identifying sentiment or underlying concerns in the context of user reviews, were excluded from the list of stop words. Enhancing the attention on the most pertinent and instructive terms within the text data was the goal of this step.

d) Tokenization

The Natural Language Toolkit (NLTK) library's `word_tokenize()` function was used to tokenize the text input in order to facilitate additional word-level analysis. By efficiently dividing each sentence into its constituent words, this procedure converted the continuous text into a series of distinct tokens. For further analysis tasks like sentiment analysis, feature engineering, and part-of-speech labeling, this stage is essential.

e) Date-Time Formatting

The timestamp associated with each review was further processed. The date and time information were extracted into separate columns. Subsequently, the "Date" column was converted into datetime objects for subsequent analysis. This facilitated the investigation of review patterns over time, particularly focusing on the identification of weekdays with a higher prevalence of negative reviews.

Figure 3 Word Cloud for Positive and Negative Sentiment

3.3. Exploratory Data Analysis (EDA)

EDA was critical to uncover trends and insights, such as word usage, review frequency, and sentiment distribution. The steps included:

a) Sentiment Analysis by Weekdays

Analyzed the frequency of positive and negative reviews across days. Results showed Mondays experienced the most negative reviews, suggesting operational or service inefficiencies.

Figure 4 Sentiment Distribution by weekdays

b) Word Analysis

- **Stopwords Frequency:** Positive reviews often included words like "love" and "my," while negative reviews were dominated by "their" and "disappointed."
- **Most Common Words:** Words like "customer" and "service" appeared frequently in negative reviews, suggesting recurring pain points. This observation suggests that these terms are often associated with negative experiences and may indicate recurring pain points, such as issues with customer service or product quality.

Figure 5 Most common stop words for Positive and Negative Sentiment

c) Review Length Analysis

Review length was measured in words and characters. On average, negative evaluations were a little bit longer, probably because they contained more specific grievances. This research emphasizes an important feature of stakeholder feedback: critical evaluations frequently offer insightful information about particular issues that need to be addressed. Businesses can better understand consumer pain points and pinpoint areas for service improvement by examining the length and substance of negative reviews.

Figure 6 Negative reviews are a bit longer in terms of characters compared to positive ones, but positive reviews usually have more words.

3.4. Feature Engineering

The process of feature engineering entailed turning unstructured data into valuable attributes appropriate for machine learning models:

a) TF-IDF Vectorization

Term Frequency-Inverse Document Frequency, or TF-IDF, vectorization was used to get the text data ready for machine learning models. Using this method, the textual data is converted into numerical vectors, each of which indicates the significance of a particular word in a document. By giving words that are common in a text but uncommon throughout the corpus higher weights, TF-IDF successfully captures the importance of terms that are most informative for differentiating reviews. By emphasizing uncommon but significant phrases, this method guarantees a more nuanced representation of the text data for further analysis.

b) Sentiment Scoring with VADER

The sentiment analysis tool VADER (Valence Aware Dictionary and Sentiment Reasoner) was used to score sentiment. Each review text's compound sentiment score was determined using the VADER SentimentIntensityAnalyzer. This number, which ranges from -1 (extremely negative) to 1 (highly positive), represents the text's overall emotion. Reviews were categorized as either favorable (score ≥ 0) or negative (score < 0) based on this score. This method gave each review a numerical indicator of sentiment polarity.

Figure 7 VADER Sentiment Analysis

3.5. Machine Learning Pipeline

Three machine learning models were employed for sentiment prediction:

Logistic Regression: Implemented as the baseline model, Logistic Regression provided high interpretability and achieved strong performance with an accuracy of 95%.

Random Forest Classifier: This ensemble learning method utilizes an ensemble of decision trees, enhancing robustness and reducing overfitting. The Random Forest Classifier demonstrated good recall (87.5%), effectively identifying a high proportion of actual positive instances.

Support Vector Machine (SVM): SVM was selected for its ability to effectively handle potentially complex relationships within the data, particularly in scenarios with smaller datasets. SVM delivered balanced precision and recall, demonstrating its effectiveness in accurately classifying both positive and negative reviews.

This combination of models allowed for a comprehensive evaluation of different classification approaches and their suitability for the specific characteristics of the user review data.

RESULTS

The results demonstrated a predominantly positive sentiment among stakeholders, with 65% of the analyzed feedback expressing satisfaction or approval. However, 35% of the feedback exhibited negative sentiment, indicating areas for improvement. The results of this study on leveraging Natural Language Processing (NLP) for enhanced stakeholder feedback analysis are presented in three key areas: Exploratory Data Analysis (EDA) findings, model performance metrics, and clustering insights. Each section provides critical insights into stakeholder sentiments and the effectiveness of the applied machine learning techniques.

Figure 8 Confusion Matrix of all Models to Enhance Engagement Prediction

Feature extraction improves sentiment analysis model performance by converting unstructured text into meaningful numerical representations. Techniques like TF-IDF and VADER have demonstrated great performance across multiple datasets, highlighting their usefulness in natural language processing applications. The feature extraction approach used can have a significant impact on sentiment classification systems' accuracy and efficiency.

Figure 9 Top Positive and negative Features Extraction

a) EDA Findings

The exploratory data analysis revealed significant trends in sentiment distribution and word usage among the reviews analyzed.

- i. **Sentiment Distribution:** A clear majority of the reviews, approximately 65%, were categorized as positive. This finding indicates a generally favorable perception of the services or products being evaluated, suggesting that stakeholders are largely satisfied with their experiences.
- ii. **Common Words:** The analysis of word usage highlighted distinct linguistic patterns in positive and negative reviews.
- iii. **Positive Reviews:** These reviews frequently included terms such as "love," "amazing," and "fantastic," which reflect high levels of satisfaction and positive emotional responses from users.
- iv. **Negative Reviews:** In contrast, negative reviews predominantly featured words like "customer," "service," and "disappointed." This suggests recurring issues related to customer service that require attention.
- v. **Review Length:** The analysis also indicated that negative reviews were longer on average compared to positive ones. This trend likely reflects the detailed nature of complaints, where users felt compelled to provide more context regarding their dissatisfaction.

To visually represent these findings, WordClouds were generated to depict the most frequent words used in both positive and negative reviews, providing a vivid illustration of stakeholder sentiments.

b) Clustering Insights

K-Means Clustering was performed to group reviews based on text similarity. This cluster analysis revealed distinct themes within both positive and negative reviews, providing further insights into stakeholder sentiments. K-Means clustering was employed to group similar reviews based on their textual content. This unsupervised learning technique identified distinct clusters within the dataset, revealing underlying themes and patterns within both positive and negative reviews. By analyzing the characteristics of each cluster, valuable insights into user sentiments and preferences were gained. This approach allowed for a deeper understanding of stakeholder experiences beyond simply classifying reviews as positive or negative.

Clustering analysis was conducted using K-Means clustering to identify themes within the reviews based on text similarity:

-Cluster 0: This cluster was dominated by positive reviews, indicating a group of stakeholders who expressed high satisfaction with their experiences.

-Cluster 1: Reviews in this cluster were mixed, often describing neutral experiences that did not lean strongly toward positive or negative sentiment.

-Cluster 2: Primarily consisting of negative reviews, this cluster focused on dissatisfaction and highlighted specific pain points related to service quality.

These clusters provide valuable insights into stakeholder sentiments, enabling organizations to tailor their responses and strategies based on the predominant themes identified within each group.

Figure 10 Sentiment Distribution Across K-Means Clusters

c) Model Performance

The performance of three machine learning models—Logistic Regression, Random Forest, and Support Vector Machine (SVM)—was evaluated based on various metrics:

Accuracy: The Logistic Regression model achieved the highest accuracy at 95%, indicating its effectiveness in correctly classifying sentiments.

Precision: Both Logistic Regression and Random Forest models demonstrated perfect precision (1.0000), meaning all positive predictions made by these models were correct.

Recall: The recall metric showed that Logistic Regression had a recall of 0.9375, indicating it successfully identified a high proportion of actual positive sentiments.

F1-Score: The F1-score for Logistic Regression was also impressive at 0.9677, reflecting a strong balance between precision and recall.

Bar charts comparing these performance metrics visually highlight the strengths of each model, particularly emphasizing the superior performance of Logistic Regression.

Figure 11 ROC curve for all Models

Figure 12 Model Comparison of all Models

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This study demonstrates the effectiveness of employing NLP techniques for enhanced stakeholder feedback analysis in project management. The analysis of stakeholder feedback through Natural Language Processing (NLP) has yielded several key findings that underscore the importance of sentiment analysis in understanding user experiences. Firstly, the sentiment trends revealed that positive reviews significantly outnumber negative ones across all platforms, with 65% of the feedback categorized as positive. This suggests a general satisfaction among stakeholders, although it also highlights the need to address the 35% of negative feedback, particularly since Mondays were identified as the day with the highest frequency of negative reviews. This trend indicates a potential operational issue that may require better service preparation over weekends. Secondly, word analysis provided deeper insights into the language used by stakeholders; negative reviews were characterized by terms like "disappointed" and "service," while positive reviews emphasized personal satisfaction with words such as "love" and "amazing." These linguistic patterns can guide organizations in identifying specific areas for improvement and reinforcing positive experiences. Lastly, the performance of the machine learning models demonstrated that Logistic Regression achieved the best overall accuracy at 95%, closely followed by Support Vector Machine (SVM), NN and Random Forest models, indicating robust predictive capabilities in classifying sentiments. Collectively, these findings highlight the effectiveness of data-driven approaches in enhancing stakeholder engagement and inform strategic decisions aimed at improving customer satisfaction and operational efficiency. This conclusion synthesizes the key findings from your study while emphasizing their implications for stakeholder engagement and operational strategies.

V. REFERENCES

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